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PROLEPSIS

Horizon Europe-funded project developing a novel personalised digital care ecosystem for people with PsA

iPROLEPSIS project newsletter | Issue No.5

July 2024

Welcome to the fifth edition of the iPROLEPSIS project newsletter! In this issue, we bring you insightful interviews with clinicians specialising in psoriatic arthritis, insights into recent clustering and networking activities, and reflections on key past events.

Inside this issue

A Spotlight on iPROLEPSIS Ongoing activities Instagram Horizon Results Booster Networking activities Events

Funded by
the European Union

iPROLEPSIS received funding from the European Union under Grant Agreement No. 101095697.

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A Spotlight on iPROLEPSIS

Interview with Dr. Laura Coates

Dr. Laura Coates, a researcher and clinician from the University of Oxford, guides through the research and clinical studies of the iPROLEPSIS project.

In her own words:

"It's my pleasure to be leading all of the clinical studies within the iPROLEPSIS Consortium. We're focused on developing and testing apps and digital health technologies to enhance the care for patients with psoriatic arthritis."

Watch the full interview [here](#).

Interview with Ilja Tchetverikov

Ilja Tchetverikov, a rheumatologist and project partner from the CICERO Foundation (the Netherlands), emphasises **the need for a deeper understanding of psoriatic arthritis**, a chronic inflammatory condition impacting various body parts due to immune system disturbances. I. Tchetverikov highlights **the project's focus on investigating disease progression factors and developing non-invasive measurement tools**.

Watch the full interview [here](#).

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Networking and clustering

Celebrating Europe Day 2024

On May 9, 2024, a joint social media campaign with our sister projects to celebrate Europe Day 2024 was organised. This initiative **aimed to highlight the themes of unity in diversity, innovation, and collaboration** across the continent.

As projects funded under the same Horizon Europe call topic, "Personalised Blueprint of Chronic Inflammation in Health-to-Disease Transition," we are **proud to contribute to the common goals of understanding the risk factors that trigger the transition from health to disease**, providing personalised prevention measures, and reducing the burden of chronic diseases.

Our collaborative efforts emphasise the importance of working together to achieve significant advancements in health research and innovation, ultimately benefiting people across Europe.

Federated AI for Privacy-Preserving Omics Profiling seminar

iPROLEPSIS had the opportunity to attend an online seminar organised by our **sister project, IMMEDIATE EU Project**. The seminar's **topic was Federated AI for Privacy-Preserving Omics Profiling**, presented by Prof. Dr. Jan Baumbach.

FeatureCloud: Some apps

- GWAS => sPLINK**
<https://exbio.wum.de/splink/>
Nasingeroh R et al. *Genome Biol.* 23(32), Jan 24, 2022.
- Gene expression => flimma**
<https://exbio.wum.de/flimma/>
Zolotareva O et al. *Genome Biol.* 23(33), Dec 14 2022.
- Time to event analysis => PaRTEA**
<https://partea.sbb.uni-hamburg.de/>
Spahn J et al. *PLoS Digit Health* 1(5): e0000101.

<https://featurecloud.ai>
Matschinski M et al. *J Med Internet Res.* 2023 Jul 12;25:e42621.

FeatureCloud: Main idea

Federated approach to big data / AI / machine learning in medicine

<https://featurecloud.ai>
Matschinski M et al. *J Med Internet Res.* 2023 (in press)

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Horizon Results Booster

The iPROLEPSIS **application for the Horizon Results Booster (HRB)**, covering both dissemination (Service 1—Module A) and exploitation (Service 2—Module C) services, **has been approved**. HRB is an initiative of the European Commission which aims to maximise the impact of public funded research within the EU.

On 26 June 2024, iPROLEPSIS held an **Exploitation Strategy Seminar** led by Horizon Results Booster expert Emmanuel Sofianopoulo. The workshop aimed **to introduce consortium partners to exploitation concepts** and help develop an exploitation strategy for project results.

Read [more](#).

Exploitation is a value driven process

Value can have different meanings:

- generate **revenues** if there are customers available to pay for the new technology/product;
- **fulfill an existing gap**;
- **increase the organization's/community's distinctive skill set and improve processes, quality (of life, of products, of services, etc.), policies, standards, etc.**

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Use

... can be
commercial, societal, political, or for improving public knowledge and action

Project partners can exploit results themselves, or facilitate exploitation by others (e.g., through making results available under open licenses)

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iPROLEPSIS joins Instagram

In March 2024, iPROLEPSIS joined the Instagram channel **to support engagement with visual content and broader audience interaction**.

Follow us on Instagram [here](#).

the patients in time to see whether or not you studies that are trying to develop and then test
to predict the development of the exacerbations and digital health technologies that might

iPROLEPSIS
A novel digital solution for psoriatic arthritis

The iPROLEPSIS project is where psoriatic arthritis inflammation is explained through multi-source data analysis guiding a novel personalised digital care ecosystem.

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this transition and model this transition in the digital world. So we want to see how the digit

Events

➤➤➤ 4th Plenary meeting

1-2 July, 2024

The iPROLEPSIS consortium met in Munich, Germany, on July 1-2, 2024, for its 4th Plenary meeting. The agenda included progress updates, workshops on IDBV (Inflammation digital biomarkers validation study) and PPIDC (Prevention of PsA inflammation through digital care: an intervention study), research advancements in digital biomarkers, ecosystem co-creation updates, and interactive sessions on Serious Games Co-Creation.

Read [more](#).

➤➤➤ IEEE MELECON 2024

25-27 June, 2024

The iPROLEPSIS breathing games presented and well received by the audience at the IEEE MELECON 2024 scientific conference. The conference was held in Porto, Portugal on 25-27 June, 2024.

Read [more](#).

IFPA Conference 2024

27-29 June, 2024

The **7th World Psoriasis & Psoriatic Arthritis Conference**, held on June 27-29, 2024, brought together leading experts and researchers to discuss the latest advancements in psoriasis and psoriatic arthritis.

Dr. Laura Coates from the University of Oxford **discussed the potential to prevent psoriatic arthritis**, including the work being done in iPROLEPSIS and HIPPOCRATES IMI.

PETRA 2024

26-28 June 2024

iPROLEPSIS was presented at PETRA 2024, a scientific interdisciplinary conference held on 26-28 June 2024 in Crete, Greece. **The iPROLEPSIS Exergames were introduced and received very positively by the audience.**

Read the full publication [here](#).

Developing Exergames for Psoriatic Arthritis using Agile Storyboarding and Game Design Processes

Bárbara Ramalho
 Marta Vicente
 Hugo Escobar
 Sandra Gama
 Filomena Carnide
 Fátima Baptista
 José A. Diniz
 Leontios J. Hadjileontiadis
 Sofia B. Dias

This project has received funding from the European Union under Grant agreement No 101095697.

2024 HIMSS European Health Conference and Exhibition

29-31 May, 2024

Project partner, PLUX Biosignals, participated in the 2024 HIMSS European Health Conference and Exhibition, where they **showcased the innovative work of the iPROLEPSIS project, developing a novel personalised digital care ecosystem for people with psoriatic arthritis.**

The 2024 HIMSS European Health Conference and Exhibition was a major event for the **European digital health community**, bringing together approximately 2,500 healthcare executives, practitioners and professionals from 84 different countries in Rome.

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International Girls in Information and Communication Technology Day – GirlSteam 2024

24 April, 2024

On 24 April 2024, we celebrated International Girls in Information and Communication Technology Day – **GirlSteam 2024**, which is part of the larger initiative, International Girls in ICT Day (Girls in ICT 2024). This annual occasion is an international effort **promoted by the United Nations agency ITU (International Telecommunication Union)**.

During this event, Bárbara Ramalho (PhD student from FMH-ULisboa) presented the iPROLEPSIS project and the iPROLEPSIS Games. The primary **aim was to raise awareness and encourage girls and young women to explore studies and careers in Information and Communication Technologies**, especially in the field of Serious Games.

British Society for Rheumatology Annual Conference

24-26 April, 2024

British Society for Rheumatology Annual Conference, the UK's leading rheumatology event, took place on 24-26 April 2024. **Dr. Laura Coates discussed preventing the transition of psoriasis to psoriatic arthritis**, including the evidence so far and studies underway with iPROLEPSIS and HIPPOCRATES IMI.

Preventing PsA

- Huge potential with easily identifiable pre-PsA population
- Need to evaluate PsA risk for individuals more accurately
- Biologics likely to reduce risk
 - Is this modification of disease evolution or masking disease
- What treatment is best – preventing disease ≠ treating disease
- What is the patient perspective on risk and acceptability of interventions

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BOTNAR KENNEDY

British Society for Rheumatology Annual Conference 24-26 April 2024